

THE PERFORMANCE OUTCOMES OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED BUSINESSES: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in global economies, making their environmental management practices important for sustainable development. Despite the growing recognition of SMEs' environmental responsibilities, there is a lack of literature that provides comprehensive insights into the performance outcomes of their environmental initiatives. This study aims to address this critical research gap by systematically examining the existing literature on the performance outcomes of environmental management in SMEs.

This review emphasises the intricate nature of conceptualising the performance outcomes of environmental management in SMEs, emphasizing its multidimensional nature and the contextual factors that shape these outcomes. It starts by identifying key performance outcomes within the existing literature, including economic performance, environmental performance, energy efficiency, waste minimization, export intensity and product innovation. While some studies suggest positive relationships between environmental management and these performance outcomes, others highlight conflicting findings, indicating that SMEs may experience diverse outcomes based on their specific circumstances. Existing research also reveals that SMEs face unique challenges in assessing and quantifying the performance outcomes of their environmental practices. These challenges, which subsequently hinders understandings of performance, include the inherent difficulties in defining environmental management performance outcomes, resolving conflicts regarding pay-back length for environmental investments, and recognising the external influences on performance measures and outcomes.

This research aims to contribute to the understanding of performance outcomes of environmental management in SMEs by synthesizing existing knowledge and revealing gaps in the literature. By mapping the landscape of available research, this review provides a foundation for future investigations, allowing scholars and practitioners to identify key areas for further inquiry and policy development. Additionally, the review underscores the need for tailored approaches to measure performance outcomes of environmental management in SMEs, recognizing that generic understandings may not adequately capture the nuances of these outcomes within the SME context. Ultimately, this literature review seeks to inform policymakers, business leaders, and researchers about the complex challenges and opportunities related to the performance outcomes of environmental management in SMEs.

Keywords: environmental management; small and medium-size enterprises; performance outcomes; literature review

1 INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are undeniably the backbone of global economies, playing a pivotal role in driving economic growth, fostering innovation, and generating employment opportunities, especially in developing countries (Elshaer et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2022). The size of SMEs can vary by country and the main criteria for distinguishing SMEs from large firms usually include the number of full-time employees and turnover (Boakye et al., 2020; Hadj, 2020). However, it is difficult to establish a universal definition of SMEs which include turnover due to the volatility of national currency values in different countries (Hadj, 2020). Therefore, in this study, SMEs are defined as those firms that have less 250 full-time employees (Boakye et al., 2020). According to Sun et al. (2022) SMEs account for approximately 90% of global business and employment, and nearly 40% of national income in developing countries. In addition, Elshaer et al. (2023) argue that these contributions are even more pronounced when informal SMEs are included.

With their significant contributions to national and international economies, the environmental management practices of SMEs hold immense importance in the context of sustainable development (Agan et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2019). Unlike the definition of SMEs, there seems to be a more universal acceptance that environmental management includes the strategies, procedures and practices of businesses aimed at preventing, controlling, or reducing the impact of their activities on the natural environment (Lee et al., 2019; Mahmud et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2011). Environmental management involve staff training; the implementation of environmental management systems (such as ISO 14001); the adoption of cleaner production activities such as reducing contamination release, energy consumption, and selecting suppliers with good environmental protection records; and conducting environmental audits (Lee et al., 2019; Mahmud et al., 2020). Despite the importance of SMES in ensuring sustainable development through their environmental management efforts, some researchers estimate that SMEs are responsible for 60–70% of global pollution (Elshaer et al., 2023). Despite the growing recognition of SMEs' environmental responsibilities, a critical research gap persists. There is a lack of a comprehensive literature that provides insights into the performance outcomes of SMEs' environmental initiatives, leaving a gap in the understanding of how these businesses contribute to broader environmental and economic objectives. This paper aims to bridge this gap by undertaking a narrative review of existing literature.

The author aims to shed light on several key aspects in the existing literature. Firstly, the various performance outcomes associated with environmental management in SMEs, including economic performance, environmental performance, energy efficiency, waste minimization, export intensity, and product innovation are identified and categorized. The review explores existing research findings, revealing both positive relationships and conflicting outcomes between environmental management practices and these performance dimensions. It underscores the idea that SMEs may experience diverse outcomes based on their unique circumstances, highlighting the need for a more nuanced approach. Furthermore, the review recognizes the unique challenges faced by SMEs in assessing and quantifying the performance outcomes of their environmental practices. These challenges encompass defining environmental management performance outcomes, addressing conflicts surrounding the payback period for environmental investments, and accounting for external influences on performance measures and outcomes. By highlighting these challenges, the authors emphasize the complexity of the SME context and the importance of tailored approaches to measuring environmental management performance outcomes.

2 METHOD

This section is to follow will provide details on the literature review methodology implemented in the present study. First, the literature search and selection strategy will be discussed. Thereafter, the inclusion and exclusion criteria used to identify relevant and credible sources will be provided. Lastly, the data extraction and analysis methods will be explained.

2.1 Literature Search and Selection

In conducting this narrative literature review, a comprehensive and systematic search of Google Scholar and EBSCOHost was undertaken. The aim was to identify relevant academic journal articles that investigated the performance outcomes of environmental management in small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). The

search included articles published between 2010 and January 2024.

The following search terms were utilized in various combinations: "SMEs," "small and medium-sized enterprises," "environmental management," "performance outcomes," "economic performance," "environmental performance." Boolean operators such as "AND" and "OR" were employed to refine and broaden the search.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Twenty-two (22) articles were included in this narrative review that met the following criteria:

- **Relevance:** The publication focused on the performance outcomes of environmental management practices within SMEs. Articles that primarily focused on larger corporations or did not directly address the performance outcomes of SMEs' environmental management practices were excluded.
- **Peer-Reviewed:** Preference was given to peer-reviewed articles published in reputable academic journals. No grey literature, reports, and conference papers were considered and only journals that appeared on the list of accredited journals of the South African Department of Higher Education and Training were included. This list includes journals found on the Norwegian, Web of Science (WoS), International Bibliography of the Social Sciences (IBSS), AOSIS & African Society for Laboratory Medicine, Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) South Africa, Scopus, the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) indices.
- **Language:** Only English-language publications were included.
- **Publication Date:** Publications between 2010 and up to the knowledge cutoff date of January 2024 were considered.
- **Full Text Availability:** Only accessible full-text articles were given priority were included.

2.3 Data Extraction and Analysis

Data extraction was carried out systematically. Information from selected articles was collected, including the publication source, author(s), publication date, research methodology used, key findings, and the performance dimensions examined (e.g., economic performance, environmental performance, energy efficiency, waste minimization, export intensity, and product innovation).

The analysis involved a qualitative synthesis of the literature. Findings were categorized, and recurring themes, patterns, and contradictions were identified. The narrative approach allowed for a critical evaluation of the literature and the construction of a coherent narrative that explained the complex relationship between environmental management and performance outcomes in SMEs.

3 DISCUSSION

This section will present the findings from the literature reviewed. Table 1 below summarises the bibliographic information of the articles included in this study.

Table 1: Bibliographic information of the articles included in this study

Author(s)	Year	Title	Publication
Cordano et al.	2010	How do Small and Medium Enterprises Go "Green"? A Study of Environmental Management Programs in the U.S. Wine Industry	Journal of Business Ethics
Martín-Tapia et al.	2010	Environmental strategy and exports in medium, small and micro-enterprises	Journal of World Business
Zeng et al.	2011	How environmental management driving forces affect environmental and economic performance of SMEs: A study in the Northern China district	Journal of Cleaner Production
Agan et al.	2013	Drivers of environmental processes and their impact on performance: A study of Turkish SMEs	Journal of Cleaner Production
Llach et al.	2013	Joint impact of quality and environmental practices on firm performance in small service businesses: An empirical study of restaurants	Journal of Cleaner Production
Arend	2014	Social and Environmental Performance at SMEs: Considering Motivations, Capabilities, and Instrumentalism	Journal of Business Ethics

Author(s)	Year	Title	Publication
O'Donohue & Torugsa	2015	The moderating effect of 'Green' HRM on the association between proactive environmental management and financial performance in small firms	International Journal of Human Resource Management
Sánchez-Medina et al.	2015	Environmental Compliance and Economic and Environmental Performance: Evidence from Handicrafts Small Businesses in Mexico	Journal of Business Ethics
Singh et al.	2015	Environmental management system ISO 14001: Effective waste minimisation in small and medium enterprises in India	Journal of Cleaner Production
Sáez-Martínez et al.	2016	Factors promoting environmental responsibility in European SMEs: The effect on performance	Sustainability
Testa et al.	2016	Factors Affecting Environmental Management by Small and Micro Firms: The Importance of Entrepreneurs' Attitudes and Environmental Investment	Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management
Christine et al.	2019	The relationship of environmental management accounting, environmental strategy and managerial commitment with environmental performance and economic performance	International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy
Lee et al.	2019	Environmental management in small and medium enterprises: the role of customer orientation and firm performance.	Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing
Boakye et al.	2020	Sustainable environmental practices and financial performance: Evidence from listed small and medium-sized enterprise in the United Kingdom	Business Strategy and the Environment
Hadj	2020	Effects of corporate social responsibility towards stakeholders and environmental management on responsible innovation and competitiveness	Journal of Cleaner Production
Johnstone	2020	The construction of environmental performance in ISO 14001-certified SMEs	Journal of Cleaner Production
Mahmud et al.	2020	Environmental management and product innovation: The moderating role of the dynamic capability of small manufacturing firms.	Journal of Cleaner Production
Nguyen & Adomako	2021	Stakeholder pressure for eco-friendly practices, international orientation, and eco-innovation: A study of small and medium-sized enterprises in Vietnam	Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management
Zahoor & Gerged	2021	Relational capital, environmental knowledge integration, and environmental performance of small and medium enterprises in emerging markets	Business Strategy and the Environment
Andersén	2022	An Attention-Based View on Environmental Management: The Influence of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Environmental Sustainability Orientation, and Competitive Intensity on Green Product Innovation in Swedish Small Manufacturing Firms	Organization and Environment
Sun et al.	2022	Green transformational leadership and environmental performance in small and medium enterprises	Economic Research-Ekonomska Istrazivanja
Elshaer et al.	2023	Green Management and Sustainable Performance of Small- and Medium-Sized Hospitality Businesses: Moderating the Role of an Employee's Pro-Environmental Behaviour	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health

The sections that follow will pay specific attention to, the key performance outcomes in existing literature, the relationships between environmental management and the outcomes identified and the challenges associated with assessing and quantifying the performance outcomes.

3.1 Key performance outcomes within the existing literature

The research articles collectively investigate a wide array of dimensions, including environmental, economic, and social performance. Some articles included specific performance outcomes related to environmental performance such as energy efficiency and waste management, while others dealt with specific economic outcomes such as exports, product innovation and competitive advantage. This reflects the multidimensional nature of environmental management practices and their impact on SMEs (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020).

3.1.1 Environmental outcomes

Environmental performance is conceptualized as the extent to which SMEs achieve environmental objectives, comply with regulations, and minimize their environmental impact, often measured through indicators such as energy consumption, waste generation, emissions, and compliance with environmental regulations, as well as the adoption of environmental management systems like ISO 14001 (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020; Zeng et al., 2011).

Sánchez-Medina et al. (2015) distinguished between subjective and objective environmental performance, evaluating perceptions of reduction in environmental impacts alongside objective lead content testing in products. This dual approach provides a comprehensive understanding of environmental performance, capturing both stakeholder perceptions and tangible environmental outcomes.

Several studies, including Testa et al. (2016) and Christine et al. (2019), utilized composite scores and factor analysis to assess environmental performance. Testa et al. (2016) derived a reliable factor representing environmental performance through common factor analysis of self-reported data on environmental targets and investments. Similarly, Christine et al. (2019) calculated composite scores based on survey responses regarding environmental management practices, strategy, and managerial commitment. These studies offer a holistic view of environmental performance by integrating multiple dimensions into composite measures.

Zahoor and Gerged (2021) and Elshaer et al. (2023) focused on compliance with environmental regulations and engagement in sustainable practices, respectively. Zahoor and Gerged (2021) measured environmental performance using a composite index of compliance, environmental management systems, initiatives, and monitoring/reporting. In contrast, Elshaer et al. (2023) assessed environmental performance through indicators related to energy conservation, waste reduction, and green market opportunities. While both studies emphasize environmental responsibility, they differ in their focus, with Zahoor and Gerged (2021) prioritizing regulatory compliance and Elshaer et al. (2023) emphasizing proactive sustainability efforts.

Sun et al. (2022) investigated the impact of green transformational leadership on environmental performance, employing quantitative measures to assess ecological impact and path analysis to understand relationships between leadership, green human resource management, innovation, and environmental outcomes. This study extends beyond traditional metrics, emphasizing the role of leadership in driving environmental performance and employing advanced statistical techniques to analyze complex relationships.

Cordano et al. (2010) and Singh et al. (2015) focused on energy reduction and waste reduction, respectively, within specific industry contexts. Energy efficiency involves SMEs' optimization of energy use and reduction of energy consumption in their operations, typically measured using indicators such as energy consumption per unit of output, adoption of energy-saving technologies, and investment in energy-efficient processes and equipment (Cordano et al., 2010). Waste management encompasses the effective handling, reduction, and disposal of waste generated by SMEs, often evaluated through indicators such as waste generation rates, recycling rates, and the implementation of waste minimization practices (Cordano et al., 2010; Singh et al., 2015). Cordano et al. (2010) utilized sets of items to measure energy reduction and recycling practices in winery operations. Similarly, Singh et al. (2015) used Likert scales to assess the extent of waste reduction in Indian SMEs. Both studies employed specific measures tailored to the industries under investigation, reflecting a customized approach to environmental performance measurement.

3.1.2 Economic outcomes

Economic performance encompasses financial indicators such as profitability, return on investment, and cost savings resulting from environmental management practices, typically measured using financial metrics like return on assets (ROA), return on investment (ROI), and market-based measures of financial performance, as well as cost savings derived from energy efficiency and waste management practices (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020; Zeng et al., 2011).

Zeng et al. (2011) adopted a comprehensive approach to measure economic performance in SMEs, encompassing both financial and non-financial indices. Financial measures included sales, profitability, inventory turnover, and return on equity (ROE), while non-financial indices comprised market share, sales region, and the number of customers. This multi-dimensional approach provides a holistic view of economic performance, recognizing the importance of both financial and non-financial factors.

Arend (2014) and Agan et al. (2013) focused on profitability and competitive advantage as key dimensions of economic performance. Arend (2014) conceptualized and measured green-based competitive advantage,

emphasizing cost reduction, product differentiation, and operational efficiency through green activities. Agan et al. (2013) considered factors such as market share, image, and long-term profits as indicators of competitive advantage, highlighting the importance of sustainability practices in enhancing economic performance.

Sánchez-Medina et al. (2015) and Llach et al. (2013) investigated economic performance using return on assets (ROA) as a financial indicator. Sánchez-Medina et al. (2015) differentiated between objective (ROA) and subjective economic performance, while Llach et al. (2013) focused on financial performance alongside market success factors such as corporate image and customer satisfaction. These studies offer insights into the financial health and market positioning of firms.

Sáez-Martínez et al. (2016) and Lee et al., (2019) examined firm performance in terms of sales growth and overall success indicators. Sáez-Martínez et al. (2016) highlighted the positive impact of Corporate Environmental Responsibility (CER) behavior on sales growth, linking environmental responsibility to economic outcomes. Lee et al., (2019) utilized both subjective perceptions and objective measures such as annual sales amount to assess firm performance, providing a comprehensive understanding of economic success.

Christine et al. (2019) and Boakye et al. (2020) employed composite scores and market-based measures to assess economic performance. Christine et al. (2019) utilized partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to analyze the influence of environmental management accounting and managerial commitment on financial outcomes. Boakye et al. (2020) measured financial performance using Return on Assets (ROA) and Tobin's q, capturing both accounting-based and market-based perspectives on economic success.

Mahmud et al. (2020) and Hadj, (2020) investigated economic performance through product innovation and competitiveness. Product innovation involves the development of new or improved products that integrate environmental considerations and sustainability principles, often assessed through indicators such as the introduction of environmentally friendly products, investment in research and development for sustainable products, and the integration of environmental criteria in the product development process (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020; Zeng et al., 2011). Mahmud et al. (2020) measured eco-product innovation through product exploration and exploitation, emphasizing the role of innovation in driving economic success. Hadj, (2020) conceptualized competitiveness in terms of product differentiation, highlighting the importance of non-price indicators in assessing SMEs' competitive advantages.

Martín-Tapia et al. (2010) provide valuable insights into the economic performance of firms by examining export intensity as a measure. Unlike studies that predominantly focus on financial indicators, their research emphasizes the significance of export activity in assessing the importance of a firm's economic performance. Export intensity, as conceptualized in the study, represents the value of exports relative to total sales. This conceptualization moves beyond mere financial measures and delves into the strategic importance of international trade for firms. By considering export intensity, the study captures the extent to which firms are engaged in global markets, reflecting their competitiveness and growth potential.

3.1.3 Social outcomes

Social performance relates to the social responsibility and impact of SMEs on stakeholders, employees, and the community, often measured using indicators such as employee satisfaction, community engagement, and adherence to social responsibility practices, with some studies also considering the impact of environmental management practices on the well-being of local communities and stakeholders (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020; Zeng et al., 2011). Only one of the articles dealt directly with social outcomes.

Elshaer et al. (2023) conceptualized and measured social performance based on indicators related to the businesses' contributions to society beyond economic interests and their interactions with stakeholders and the community. The authors included the following dimensions:

- Relationship with the community and stakeholders: Improved interactions and engagement with the local community, customers, suppliers, and other stakeholders.
- Work safety: Initiatives to enhance workplace safety and employee well-being.
- Living quality of the surrounding community: Efforts to improve the quality of life and well-being of the local community.

3.2 Relationships between Environmental Management and Performance Outcomes

Some studies found that environmental management positively affects environmental, economic, and social performance, leading to sustainable performance (Elshaer et al., 2023). For instance, a study conducted in India found that green management practices (GMPs) can improve environmental, economic, and social performance, and these relationships can be strengthened through the moderating effects of employees' pro-environmental behavior (Elshaer et al., 2023). Similarly, a study conducted in the United Kingdom found that the adoption of environmental management systems such as ISO 14001 has been reflected in improvements in financial performance over time (Singh et al., 2015).

Several studies have highlighted the positive impact of energy efficiency on the environmental and economic performance of SMEs. Energy efficiency practices not only contribute to cost savings but also reduce environmental impact. For instance, a study in the primary metals manufacturing sector found that energy efficiency practices positively influenced financial performance (Andersén, 2022). However, challenges related to resource and knowledge constraints were identified, indicating the need for targeted support programs to enhance SMEs' capability to innovate and improve their environmental and financial performance (Boakye et al., 2020).

Effective waste minimization practices have been shown to enhance financial performance in SMEs. Waste minimization not only reduces costs associated with waste disposal but also demonstrates environmental responsibility. However, the implementation of waste minimization practices in SMEs can be challenging due to resource and knowledge constraints. Therefore, targeted investment and training support programs are essential to assist SMEs in developing the capability to innovate and improve their environmental and financial performance (Boakye et al., 2020; Martín-Tapia et al., 2010).

However, the relationship between environmental management and competitive advantage over time provides divergent findings, depending on the considered dimensions and measurements for environmental actions (Elshaer et al., 2023). For instance, a study conducted in Turkey found that the impact of environmental management practices on competitive advantage is not significant. Moreover, poor financial performance reflected over time has been found to provide a broader indication of sustainable development (Elshaer et al., 2023).

Environmental management practices have been found to positively influence SMEs' export performance. Studies have indicated that environmental policies and innovation can have a positive impact on SMEs' export performance (Martín-Tapia et al., 2010). However, the relationship between environmental management practices and export performance may be influenced by various contextual factors, and the specific mechanisms through which environmental practices influence export performance require further exploration.

Environmental management practices have been linked to enhanced product innovation in SMEs. The implementation of environmental management practices can stimulate product innovation, leading to the development of environmentally friendly and sustainable products. However, challenges related to resource and knowledge constraints have been identified, emphasizing the need for targeted support programs to enhance SMEs' capability to innovate and improve their environmental and financial performance (Boakye et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the studies suggest that the impact of environmental management practices on SMEs' performance is influenced by various factors such as managerial commitment, green HRM, and employees' pro-environmental behavior. The moderating effect of green HRM on the association between proactive environmental management and financial performance in small firms has been validated (O'Donohue & Torugsa, 2015). Green HRM practices such as developing and enhancing employees' skills, knowledge, and abilities; motivating employees by investing in them, encouraging commitment, and caring for employees; and providing opportunities for involving employees in decision-making have been found to contribute to the enhancement of the business and financial benefits a small firm can derive from the implementation of a proactive approach to environmental management (O'Donohue & Torugsa, 2015).

The employees' pro-environmental behavior variable has been found to positively moderate the relationship between green management and sustainable performance (Elshaer et al., 2023). A study conducted in Indonesia found that antecedents of environmental management accounting and environmental performance evidence from Indonesian small and medium enterprises are influenced by employees' pro-environmental behavior (Elshaer et al., 2023). Similarly, a study conducted in Vietnam found that stakeholder pressure for

eco-friendly practices, international orientation, and eco-innovation are positively related to environmental performance, and this relationship is moderated by employees' pro-environmental behavior (Nguyen & Adomako, 2021).

3.3 Challenges in Assessing and Quantifying the Performance Outcomes of Environmental Management

Assessing and quantifying the performance outcomes of environmental practices is a complex and challenging task for researchers and practitioners alike. One of the main challenges is the inherent difficulties in defining environmental management performance outcomes. Environmental performance is a multidimensional construct that encompasses a wide range of indicators, including energy consumption, waste generation, emissions, and compliance with environmental regulations, among others (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020; Zeng et al., 2011). However, there is no consensus on which indicators to use, how to measure them, and how to aggregate them into a single measure of environmental performance (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020). This lack of standardization makes it difficult to compare the environmental performance of different SMEs and to assess the impact of environmental management practices on performance outcomes.

Another challenge is resolving conflicts regarding pay-back length for environmental investments. Environmental management practices often require significant investments in new technologies, equipment, and processes, which can have a long pay-back period (Zeng et al., 2011). This can create conflicts between short-term financial goals and long-term environmental objectives, making it difficult for SMEs to justify the investment in environmental management practices (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020). Moreover, the benefits of environmental management practices are often intangible and difficult to quantify, such as improved reputation, increased customer loyalty, and reduced regulatory risks (Zeng et al., 2011). This further complicates the assessment of the financial and non-financial benefits of environmental management practices.

Recognizing the external influences on performance measures and outcomes is another challenge. SMEs operate in a complex and dynamic environment that is shaped by a wide range of external factors, including regulatory frameworks, market conditions, and stakeholder expectations (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020). These external factors can have a significant impact on the performance outcomes of environmental management practices, making it difficult to isolate the effects of environmental management practices from other external factors (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020). For example, the impact of environmental management practices on export performance may be influenced by factors such as exchange rates, trade policies, and market demand, which are beyond the control of SMEs (Johnstone & Hallberg, 2020).

4 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to address the research gap in the environmental management by systematically examining the existing literature on the performance outcomes of environmental management in SMEs. The diverse conceptualization and operationalization of the performance outcomes investigated across the studies underscore the complex and multifaceted relationship between environmental management practices and SME performance.

Overall, the studies suggested that environmental management practices can have positive outcomes on SMEs' performance, but the impact may vary depending on the specific context and factors influencing the relationship. Therefore, SMEs should focus on creating a culture of environmental stewardship and actively involve employees in green initiatives to enhance sustainable performance.

Energy efficiency, waste management, export, and product innovation are critical aspects of environmental management practices in SMEs. While the literature demonstrates the positive impact of these practices on SMEs' environmental and economic performance, it also highlights the challenges associated with resource and knowledge constraints. Therefore, targeted support programs are essential to assist SMEs in developing the capability to innovate and improve their environmental and financial performance.

Assessing and quantifying the performance outcomes of environmental practices is a challenging task that requires careful consideration of the multidimensional nature of environmental, economic and social performance, the conflicts between short-term financial goals and long-term environmental objectives, and the external influences on performance measures and outcomes. Standardization of performance indicators and the development of robust methodologies for assessing the financial and non-financial benefits of

environmental management practices are needed to overcome these challenges and to promote the adoption of sustainable practices by SMEs.

It is essential to acknowledge the potential limitations of this narrative literature review. While efforts were made to conduct a comprehensive search, some relevant publications may have been inadvertently excluded or were not accessible to the researcher. Additionally, the focus on English-language sources may have resulted in the omission of valuable non-English research. The review's findings are based on existing literature up to January 2024, and subsequent research may have emerged since that time.

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